

Appendix for Conference Paper "Data Governance Practices
for Generative AI Powered Organizational Knowledge
Management Systems Using Retrieval Augmented
Generation"

September 4, 2025

1 Detailed Literature Review Results

As mentioned in the main text, given the field’s novelty and rapid development, peer-reviewed publications are rare; therefore preprints and grey literature were included. The literature review also served mainly as the basis for the interview guide and to guide follow-up questions.

Theme	Data Governance Practice	Sources
Data Quality	Implementation technical procedures to assess data before it is ingested in the data pipeline	Gokul et al. (2025), Panda and Mukherjee (2025), Prabhune and Berndt (2024), and Rupanagunta et al. (2024)
	Regular evaluation of parsed data by manually reviewing a sample of the output	Microsoft (2024b)
	Establishment of clear guidelines for data handling, storage, and retrieval to maintain integrity of information used by RAG systems	Prabhune and Berndt (2024)
	Usage of data quality metrics to decide which data is ingested into RAG	Rupanagunta et al. (2024)
	Monitor data quality measures through KPIs	Papagiannidis et al. (2023)
Content Guidelines	Guidelines to optimize content for RAG, e.g., explain graphics in text, add summaries to tutorials, simplify complex tables, enable consistency	Packowski et al. (2024) and Soman and Roychowdhury (2024)
Metadata	Implement policies and controls to ensure relevant metadata such as confidentiality is included	Ramachandran (2024)
	Include license metadata to ensure compliance	Meroño-Peñuela et al. (2025)
	Usage of data catalogues to extend metadata in RAG system	Rupanagunta et al. (2024)
Access Controls	Implement access controls for embeddings in vector database using ACLs	Akkiraju et al. (2024), Google (2025), Panda and Mukherjee (2025), Prabhune and Berndt (2024), Rupanagunta et al. (2024), and Shi et al. (2024)
	Policy enforcement using GenAI to evaluate access requests contextually and complement RBAC/PBAC mechanisms	Rupanagunta et al. (2024)
Data Privacy & Sensitivity	Implement data sensitivity classifications and define what data is eligible for inclusion	Akkiraju et al. (2024) and Google (2025)
	Careful consideration and coordination regarding the implementation of PII (personally identifiable information) and Sensitive Information	Akkiraju et al. (2024), Panda and Mukherjee (2025), and Papagiannidis et al. (2023)
	Replace or remove PII in data using data masking algorithms	Haridasan (2024), Panda and Mukherjee (2025), Rupanagunta et al. (2024), and Sun et al. (2024)
Monitor Data	Creation of detailed audit logs for all data access and usage within the RAG system	Google (2025), Panda and Mukherjee (2025), and Prabhune and Berndt (2024)
	Define toxicity scoring to evaluate responses for harmful or inappropriate content	Haridasan (2024)
	Track data use with dashboard	Papagiannidis et al. (2023)
Overview and Accessibility	Develop API governance policies and standards, including comprehensive API catalogue	Ramachandran (2024)
	Data cataloguing or labelling for easier source identification	Pahune et al. (2025)
	Centralized repositories for better accessibility	Pahune et al. (2025)
Trainings	Create trainings for users of the AI system on data privacy, confidentiality, and data policy awareness and efficient use	Papagiannidis et al. (2023) and Prabhune and Berndt (2024)

Table 1: Data Governance Practices for RAG-enhanced LLMs in Literature

2 Literature Review: Overview of Relevant Work

Author	Name of Paper	Type of Paper	Description
Akkiraju et al. (2024)	FACTS About Building Retrieval Augmented Generation-based Chatbots	Preprint	NVIDIA’s framework for enterprise RAG chatbots including data governance
Microsoft (2024b)	Improve RAG application quality	Practice Literature	Describes how to refine RAG components to increase quality using Azure Databricks
Gokul et al. (2025)	Contradiction Detection in RAG Systems: Evaluating LLMs as Context Validators for Improved Information Consistency	Preprint	Evaluates LLMs’ ability to detect contradictions in retrieved context for improved consistency
Google (2025)	Infrastruktur für eine RAG-fähige generative KI-Anwendung mit Vertex AI und Vektorsuche	Practice Literature	Infrastructure guide for RAG apps using Google’s GenAI tools; mentions data governance like sensitivity classification
Haridasan (2024)	The Salesforce Einstein Trust Layer for Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) for Enterprise Applications	Peer-reviewed Article	Proposes implementation of a “Salesforce Einstein Trust Layer” in deploying RAG models to ensure data privacy standards are met while delivering AI-generated responses
Meroño-Peñuela et al. (2025)	KG.GOV: Knowledge graphs as the backbone of data governance in AI	Peer-reviewed Article	Proposes knowledge graphs as a governance layer in AI, including three framework dimensions; refers to RAG use cases
Microsoft (2024a)	Improve RAG application quality.	Practice Literature	Presents different ways to improve the application quality of RAG, including data quality related aspects
Packowski et al. (2024)	Optimizing and Evaluating Enterprise Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG): A Content Design Perspective	Conference	Proposes document content design strategies to enhance RAG system effectiveness
Pahune et al. (2025)	The Importance of AI Data Governance in Large Language Models	Preprint	Proposes AI Data Governance Framework for LLMs; outlines its importance for building trust
Panda and Mukherjee (2025)	ENHANCING PRIVACY AND SECURITY IN RAG-BASED GENERATIVE AI APPLICATIONS	Conference	Explores privacy/security frameworks for RAG; proposes data governance to reduce data leakage/compliance risk
Papagiannidis et al. (2023)	Toward AI Governance: Identifying Best Practices and Potential Barriers and Outcomes	Peer-reviewed Article	Extracts best practices for AI governance through three case studies involving RAG
Prabhune and Berndt (2024)	Deploying Large Language Models With Retrieval Augmented Generation	Preprint Article	Provides best practices and governance recommendations for adopting RAG-enhanced LLMs in regulated industries
Ramachandran (2024)	Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) for Large Language Models Leveraging Enterprise Data (SAP, Salesforce, Workday)	Practice Literature	Describes design decisions for RAG-enhanced LLMs accessing current enterprise data from systems like SAP, Workday, and Salesforce
Rupanagunta et al. (2024)	Data governance in the age of generative AI	Practice Literature	Presents a data pipeline and user query workflow for RAG-enhanced LLMs that access internal structured/unstructured data, with technical-level data governance mechanisms
Shi et al. (2024)	Meta data retrieval for data infrastructure via RAG	Conference Article	Proposes a RAG-based architecture for metadata-enhanced data exploration
Soman and Roychowdhury (2024)	Observations on Building RAG Systems for Technical Documents	Preprint	Explores factors that influence the quality of RAG for retrieving technical content
(Sun et al., 2024)	From Principles to Practice: A Deep Dive into AI Ethics and Regulations	Preprint Article	Discusses practical application of EU AI regulation including governance practices for RAG

Table 2: Appendix: Overview of relevant literature

3 Semi-structured Interview Guide

PART I: GENERAL INFORMATION	
Firm and KMS Specifics	<i>Can you introduce your company? Can you describe the purpose and area of application of the KMS? Can you describe the current status (maturity) of the KMS?</i>
PART II: DESIGN OF KMS	
Accessed Data	<i>Which data is being accessed? Which format? How would you classify its sensitivity? Does it contain PII? Is external data ingested as well?</i>
Model	<i>Which AI model does the KMS use? Why was it selected?</i>
Data Pipeline	<i>Can you describe the data pipeline(s)? Describe the parsing process. Which chunking strategy is used? How are embeddings created? Are indexing techniques used?</i>
Inference Chain	<i>Can you describe the inference chain? Which retrieval approach is used? What is the search strategy? Which prompt augmentation and pre- and post-processing steps are taken?</i>
PART III: DATA GOVERNANCE PRACTICES	
Knowledge Quality	Main: <i>Which data governance practices are used/planned/discussed to enhance the quality of the knowledge accessed by the RAG system (e.g., enhanced data curation, data quality and metadata)?</i> Follow-up: <i>How were the relevant knowledge sources identified? How was decided which are relevant? How is the accuracy of the information/data controlled and who is responsible? Are metadata enrichment techniques used? Which metadata is added? Where there practices that helped to ensure their population?</i>
System Quality	Main: <i>Which data governance practices are used to maximize the system quality (e.g., enhanced retrieval process and automatization of data integration processes)?</i> Follow-up: <i>How can data be processed for faster or more efficient retrieval? Are there ontologies or taxonomies helping the user for prompt formulation? Are there practices allowing for faster development of data pipelines or making them more effective? How is the data processed to allow faster or more relevant retrieval? How are APIs integrated?</i>
Service Quality	Main: <i>Which data governance practices are used to maximize the service quality (e.g., controlling and monitoring of risks, security)?</i> Follow-up: <i>How are PII or sensitive information handled? How was the decision made to include/not include them? How is ensured that no sensible or protected data is unwillingly disclosed? How are data-related risks identified and managed? How are access controls implemented?</i>
Ending Question	<i>Were any other data governance practices used or discussed that were not already mentioned?</i>
PART IV: SUCCESS OF KMS	
Success	<i>How would you define the overall success of the KMS? How do you think the data governance practices contributed to that?</i>

Table 3: Semi-structured interview guide (initial consolidated version, updated iteratively)

References

- Akkiraju, R., Xu, A., Bora, D., Yu, T., An, L., Seth, V., Shukla, A., Gundecha, P., Mehta, H., Jha, A., Raj, P., Balasubramanian, A., Maram, M., Muthusamy, G., Annepally, S. R., Knowles, S., Du, M., Burnett, N., Javiya, S., . . . Boitano, J. (2024, July). FACTS About Building Retrieval Augmented Generation-based Chatbots [arXiv:2407.07858 [cs]]. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2407.07858>
- Gokul, V., Tenneti, S., & Nakkiran, A. (2025, March). Contradiction Detection in RAG Systems: Evaluating LLMs as Context Validators for Improved Information Consistency [arXiv:2504.00180 [cs]]. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2504.00180>
- Google. (2025, March). Infrastruktur für eine RAG-fähige generative KI-Anwendung mit Vertex AI und Vektorsuche. Retrieved March 31, 2025, from <https://cloud.google.com/architecture/gen-ai-rag-vertex-ai-vector-search?hl=de>
- Haridasan, P. K. (2024). The Salesforce Einstein Trust Layer for Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) for Enterprise Applications. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management*, 08(10), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.55041/IJSREM28465>
- Meroño-Peñuela, A., Simperl, E., Kurteva, A., & Reklós, I. (2025). KG.GOV: Knowledge graphs as the backbone of data governance in AI. *Journal of Web Semantics*, 85, 100847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.websem.2024.100847>
- Microsoft. (2024a, October). AI and machine learning on Databricks. Retrieved January 3, 2025, from <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/databricks/machine-learning/>
- Microsoft. (2024b, October). Improve RAG application quality. Retrieved January 3, 2025, from <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/databricks/generative-ai/tutorials/ai-cookbook/quality-overview>
- Packowski, S., Halilovic, I., Schlotfeldt, J., & Smith, T. (2024). Optimizing and Evaluating Enterprise Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG): A Content Design Perspective. *Proceedings of the 2024 8th International Conference on Advances in Artificial Intelligence*, 162–167. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3704137.3704181>
- Pahune, S., Akhtar, Z., Mandapati, V., & Siddique, K. (2025, April). The Importance of AI Data Governance in Large Language Models. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202504.0219.v1>
- Panda, M., & Mukherjee, S. (2025). Enhancing Privacy and Security in Rag-Based Generative AI Applications. *AI, Machine Learning and Applications advances 2025*, 01–10. <https://doi.org/10.5121/csit.2025.150301>
- Papagiannidis, E., Enholm, I. M., Dremel, C., Mikalef, P., & Krogstie, J. (2023). Toward AI Governance: Identifying Best Practices and Potential Barriers and Outcomes. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 25(1), 123–141. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-022-10251-y>
- Prabhune, S., & Berndt, D. J. (2024, November). Deploying Large Language Models With Retrieval Augmented Generation [arXiv:2411.11895 [cs]]. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2411.11895>
- Ramachandran, A. (2024, August). Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) for Large Language Models Leveraging Enterprise Data (SAP, Salesforce, Workday). Retrieved December 29, 2024, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/383561133_Retrieval_Augmented_Generation_RAG_for_Large_Language_Models_Leveraging_Enterprise_Data_SAP_Salesforce_Workday
- Rupanagunta, K., Arni, R., & Sayed, I. (2024, February). Data governance in the age of generative AI. Retrieved December 12, 2024, from <https://aws.amazon.com/de/blogs/big-data/data-governance-in-the-age-of-generative-ai/>

- Shi, Z.-F., Liu, K., Bai, S., Jiang, Y.-T., Huo, T., Jing, X., Li, R.-Z., & Ma, X.-J. (2024). Meta data retrieval for data infrastructure via RAG. *2024 IEEE International Conference on Web Services (ICWS)*, 100–107. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICWS62655.2024.00029>
- Soman, S., & Roychowdhury, S. (2024, March). Observations on Building RAG Systems for Technical Documents [arXiv:2404.00657 [cs]]. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2404.00657>
- Sun, N., Miao, Y., Jiang, H., Ding, M., & Zhang, J. (2024). From Principles to Practice: A Deep Dive into AI Ethics and Regulations [Version Number: 1]. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2412.04683>